

Research Paper

Nigeria's Anti-Corruption Institutions and Fight Against Corruption: A Morality Approach

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18677963>

Received 05, 02 2026; Accepted 12 02, 2026© The author(s)2026. Published with open access at www.rapidjournals.com

ABSTRACT:The activities of Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions have increasingly raised grave concerns in recent times with regard to the fight against corruption in the country. This is more so, as corruption is daily assuming wider spread and penetrating the fabrics of institutions that are established to fight corruption. This paper, explored Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions and their failures in fighting corruption. The paper is anchored on Kohlberg's theory of moral development. This is because morality is the fulcrum and base upon which corruption and corrupt practices are fanned. The theory focuses on how moral logic is primarily the bases for seeking and maintaining justice with regard to the fight against corruption. Data for this paper is mainly secondary. Thus, the qualitative-descriptive model was employed as a strategy for gathering and analyzing generated data. Accordingly, qualitative content analysis procedures were adopted to analyze generated data. The paper concluded that the absence of moral correctness in the formation of Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions and the prebendal system of appointments and selections of its officials without professionalism is hugely responsible for the failures of these institutions. Accordingly, the findings revealed that political and judicial interferences in the course of justice administration in the fight against corruption in itself is short of moral correctness. The paper recommends among others; that for Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions not to falter or fail in its fight against corruption, the functions and selections of its officials should be done on the basis of obtaining moral correctness and moral justice in the fight against corruption.

Keywords: Anti-corruption, judiciary, institution, morality, moral development, moral logic, moral correctness, moral justice, prebendal system, Failures.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, anti-corruption campaigns have been embraced as a major challenge in a considerable number of countries, notably in the third world and in particular, the Sub-Saharan Africa. In Nigeria, this was one of the major policy priorities that influenced President Olusegun Obasanjo administration in 1999, in addition with international pressure to create anti-corruption institutions such as the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offenses Commission (ICPC) and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) to fight corruption. Upon creation of the two institutions, surprisingly to those who doubted their workability, they immediately embarked on a comprehensive anti-corruption agenda aimed at redressing Nigeria's economic decline and badly tarnished international image. The measures President Obasanjo administration implemented to achieve the anti-corruption policies included: Reform of the public services; accelerated privatization; reform of the management of public revenue and expenditures; design and implementation of new criteria for employment; remuneration for public service;

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reform of the judiciary; establishment of anti-corruption agencies being the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC)); a global campaign aimed at checking the diversion of public funds abroad and the recovery of assets already siphoned out of the country. Enwerem (2012). Even though these measures are not new in global anti-corruption policy circles, they still raised unprecedented interest and attention locally and internationally. Thus, locally, the interest and doubts of the workability of President Obasanjo's anti-corruption institutions were based on previous and existing policies that haven't worked in Nigeria.

According to Onya and Eleanya (2016), Nigeria's corruption has emanated from historical, economic, political, geographical, cultural and social factors. In all of these, corruption, and in particular official corruption remains a controversial issue in all typologies of governments since her amalgamation in 1914. Therefore, to them, there exists unresolved approach in the policies of past governments to fight and minimize corruption both in the public and private sectors. Referrals were made to failures of past and existing laws and policies such as: Section 15(5) of the extant constitution of 1960 that mandated the Head of State to abolish all corrupt practices and abuse of powers; the 1999 constitution, in section 23, that itemized 'national ethics' that are antithetical to corruption; section 88 and 89, that empowered the National Assembly to expose corruption, inefficiency and waste in government through probe and investigations; while APC, the ruling party's constitution in item No.4 takes clear position on strict enforcement of anti-corruption laws (ibid). It is disheartening to note that corruption hasn't been killed or minimized in Nigeria till date, aside past and present laws, policies, including institutions created for it. Rather, corruption is daily assuming wider spread and even penetrating the institutions fabrics that should fight it. Hence, the major contribution among others that this paper is adding to literature in this field of study is the identification of some salient analytical and social insights of political and judicial interferences without moral correctness in the course of justice administration of anti-corruption institutions that has caused their failures. While the meticulous and methodical analytical persuasion theory that the paper adopted is Kohlberg's theory of moral development that focuses on the foundations of how people develop morality and moral reasoning and how moral logic is primarily focused on seeking and maintaining justice. In addition, how moral development theory is the process by which people develop the distinction between right and wrong and engage in reasoning between the two.

II. Analytical Persuasion Theory (APT).

The analytical persuasion theory that will underpin "Nigeria's Anti-Corruption Institutions and the fight against corruption: morality approach is Kohlberg's theory of moral development. This is so because morality is the fulcrum and the cause of Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions failures. Kohlberg's theory focuses on the foundations of how people develop morality and moral reasoning. It suggests that moral development occurs in a series of six stages and that moral logic is primarily focused on seeking and maintaining justice. The theory further posits that moral development is the process by which people develop the distinction between right and

wrong and engage in reasoning between the two. It's apt at this point to understand that Jean Piaget is the precursor of this theory but Lawrence Kohlberg extended it and proposed that moral development is a continual process that occurs throughout the lifespan. Thus, Kohlberg's theory outlines six stages of moral development within three different levels that explained why it's the most suitable theory for this study.

Stages of Moral Development

Kohlberg's theory is broken down into three primary levels. At each level of moral development, there are two stages. Similar to how Piaget believed that not all people reach the highest levels of cognitive development, Kohlberg believed not everyone progresses to the highest stages of moral development Kendra (2022). Levels of Moral Development Age Stages Included in This Level Preconventional Morality 0 to 9. Stage 1: Obedience and punishment Stage 2: Individualism and exchange Conventional Morality Early adolescence to adulthood Stage 3: Developing good interpersonal relationships Stage 4: Maintaining social order Postconventional Morality Some adults; rare Stage 5: Social contract and individual rights stage 6: Universal principles Level 1. Preconventional Morality Preconventional morality is the earliest period of moral development. It lasts until around the age of nine. At this age, children's decisions are primarily shaped by the expectations of adults and the consequences of breaking the rules. There are two stages within this level: . Stage 1 Obedience and Punishment: The earliest stages of moral development, obedience and punishment are especially common in young children, but adults are also capable of expressing this type of reasoning. According to Kohlberg, people at this stage see rules as fixed and absolute. Obeying the rules is important because it is a way to avoid punishment. ii. Stage 2

Individualism and Exchange: At the individualism and exchange stage of moral development, children account for individual points of view and judge actions based on how they serve individual needs. In this case, children argued that the best course of action was the choice that best served oneself. Reciprocity is possible at this point in moral development, but only if it serves one's own interests. Level 2. Conventional Morality: The next period of moral development is marked by the acceptance of social rules regarding what is good and moral. During this time, adolescents and adults internalize the moral standards they have learned from their role models and from society. This period also focuses on the acceptance of authority and conforming to the norms of the group. There are two stages at this level of morality: iii. Stage 3 Developing Good Interpersonal Relationships: Often referred to as the "good boy-good girl" orientation, this stage of the interpersonal relationship of moral development is focused on living up to social expectations and roles.

There is an emphasis on conformity, being nice and consideration of how choices influence relationships. iv. Stage 4 Maintaining Social Order: This stage is focused on ensuring that social order is maintained. At this stage of moral development, people begin to consider society as a whole when making judgments. The focus is on maintaining law and order by following the rules, doing one's duty, and respecting authority. Level 3. Postconventional Morality At this level of moral development, people develop an understanding of abstract principles of morality. The two stages at this level are: v. Stage 5 Social Contract and Individual Rights: The ideas of a social contract and individual rights cause people in the next stage to begin to account for the differing values, opinions, and beliefs of other people. Rules of law are important for maintaining a society, but members of the society should agree upon these standards. vi. Stage 6 Universal Principles: This is Kohlberg's final level of moral reasoning that is based on universal ethical principles and abstract reasoning. At this stage, people follow these internalized principles of justice, even if they conflict with laws and rules. From the above analytical persuasion of the theory, this study is of the understanding that the religious application of Kohlberg's theory of moral development in all administrative policies of Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions, be it short time, medium time and even long time will sure forestall anti-corruption institutions failures in Nigeria.

CONCEPTUAL EXPLICATION OF ANTI-CORRUPTION INSTITUTIONS FAILURES IN NIGERIA

In order to have a better understanding of Nigeria's Anti Corruption Institutions Fight Against Corruption: Morality Approach, we shall discuss the conceptual explication of its causes. Corruption in Nigeria represents dishonesty, bribery embezzlement and illicit transactions. It's a shameful act but yet the actors involved in it in Nigeria are defended and celebrated by their families, kinsmen and even coreligionists because of the act of prebendalism or prebendal system in Nigeria's political and judiciary institutions. Ironically, family institutions, religious institutions, academics institutions, judiciary institutions and even anti-corruption institutions that should reproach and fight corruption are culpable intentionally or unintentionally, due to their lack of moral correctness and justice to fight corruption in Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions

Prebendalism or prebendal system Prebendalism refers to political systems in which elected officials and government workers feel they have a right to a share of government revenues, and they use them to benefit supporters, co-religionists and members of their ethnic group. (<https://en.wikipedia.org>. Assessed 8/12/2024). This act of prebendalism or prebendal system has contributed colossally to Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions failure in fighting corruption. A case that will be considered by this paper to justify this is that of Abdurashheed Maina, the former chairman of the Pension Reform Task Force Team, that was involved in a massive corruption scandal. He was accused of operating fictitious bank accounts, corruption, and money laundering to the tune of N2 billion. (Punch, 2018). His corruption scheme involved stealing pension funds, with about N14 billion stolen from the pension account. He also used fake identities and companies to launder the money. For instance, he used his sister's name to open a bank account, which had a turnover of over N300 million. However, aside the empirical facts presented to the relevant authorities, his kinsmen from Borno state protested of injustice meted on their kinsman, Maina. The then Attorney General of the Federation and Minister of Justice, Abubakar Malami who should be more interested to prosecute Maina, as the Chief Law Officer of Nigeria Federation was rather preparing a soft landing for Maina not to be tried by Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), one of Nigeria's famous anti-corruption institutions. The then Chief of Staff to President Buhari, Abba Kyari defended Maina against the position of the then Head of Civil Service, Madam Winifred Oyo-Ita that wanted Maina tried in

a competent court of the land. This her position almost cost her, her job through the Chief of Staff to President Buhari. The legislative arm wasn't left out as the Senator representing Maina's senatorial district in Borno state, Senator Ndume did all within his reach to ensure that his on bail. The State Security Service (SSS), Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and the Nigeria Correctional Service (NCoS) were all laying claim on who should be in custody of Maina constitutionally for selfish interests primarily (Punch, 2018). This scenario justified Onya and Eleanya (2016) position on if "President Buhari's anti-corruption policy is a reality or an illusion"? Indeed, from all empiricism, Maina's corruption case epitomizes prebendalism or prebendal system, as such, it's one of the cases that this paper believes that caused Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions failure in fighting corruption.

Religious Institutions Religious institutions are Churches, temples, mosques and other places of worship and institutions that exist to support and manage the practice of a specific set of religious beliefs. In Nigeria, it has different opinions, objectives and roles such as: social change, social cohesion, peace building, community development, moral education, sustainable development and sensitization against social vices such as the Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions failures in fighting corruption. Thus, probably the rational why David (2015) is of the opinion that Religion should be considered on opinion rather than a fact. In Nigeria religious institutions, such as some of the New Generation Pentecostal Churches, that majored in "Prosperity Preachings and or teachings, should know that their preachings and or teachings in some cases, unintentionally mislead some of their members opinions who are not knowledgeable enough to dissect, analyze and understand their good intended preachings or teachings from the Holy Bible. As such, it's apt for the preachers or teachers to note that one of the objectives why some Nigerians go to their religious institutions, is to seek redemption, reconciliation and good life aside Karl Marx perception of "religion, as an opium of the people" David (2015). Hence, this paper is of the opinion that it beholds on the preachers and teachers of the Nigerias religious institutions to lay more emphasis on morality or moral correctness preachings and teachings in order to fight corruption in Nigeria's anti corruption institutions. This is more so because most of the officials of the Nigeria's anti corruption institutions are members of Nigeria's Religious Institutions.

A case study, this paper examines to illustrate how preachers and teachers of Nigerias Religious Institutions preaching and teaching could mislead opinions of their members and in particular, those members working in Nigerias anticorruption institutions that have led to the cause of Nigerias Anticorruption institutions failure in fighting corruption is that of Past Taiwo Odukoya's 3/1/2021 Sunday preaching titled "Possessing your Possessions", (Odukoya, 2021). Taking his theme scripture from the Book of Obadiah 1:17, which also is the theme scripture for the year, the clergy noted that to possess one's possession means to take ownership of everything Christ has finished for one. He further cited examples of Biblical characters like Abraham (Genesis 13:10-17) and Joshua (Joshua 1), who, remaining in their covenant spaces were able to possessed their possessions. He noted that being courageous, strong, and obedient to God's commandments are very important for believers if they must possess their possessions.

Pastor Taiwo went on to admonish his members against taking their eyes off Jesus as that would be their undoing. "You may still look and think you are sustained because you are licking the dust off the feet of men, but in the end, they will deal with you." He then highlighted taking back what was taken, capturing the grounds and claiming and walking in the inheritance and indwelling of the Holy Spirit as three important things every believer must do in order to possess their possessions. Scripture references to the above points can be drawn from Deuteronomy 9:1-3, Joshua 1 and Ephesians 1:3-11 respectively (Odukoya, 2021). From the point of this preaching, this paper is of the opinion that some members of this religious sect institution and in particular, those working with Nigeria's Anticorruption Institutions that are not knowledgeable enough to dissect, analyze and understand the good intentions of the Holy Bible's quotes on it may be misled with wrong opinions. Thus, its position of emphasis on moral correctness preachings and teachings in Nigerias Religious Institutions by their preachers or teachers. This is apt so that Nigerias Anticorruption

institutions will not fail or falter to fight corruption, as most of their workers or officials are members of Nigerias Religious Institutions. Similarly, it's important to recognize Kohlberg's position on morality, so as to appreciate the importance of moral correctness preachings and teachings in Nigeria's Religious institutions. This is more so because its understanding will help in fighting corruption in Nigeria's Anti corruptions Institutions. To Kohlberg, morality is the fulcrum and base upon which corruption and corrupt

practices are fanned. Kohlberg & Candee(1984).Family Institutions The family is a fundamental institution that plays an integral role in shaping the moral values, beliefs, and character of its members. This is achieved through norms, emotional support, socialization and role modeling. Families transmit moral values and establish norms to guide members to make responsible choices. As the first point of contact for children, families lay the foundation for moral development, influencing individuals to become responsible and morally upright members of society. The family is expected to pass on the societal values to their children such as respect for others, self control, goodness, altruism, truth, fairness and honesty (Uwe, Asuquo & Ekuri, 2008).

The point being established here is that if families instill the above societal values in their child, it will be difficult to see such a child in fraudulent acts such as corrupt practices that has led to Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions failure in fighting corruption when the child grows up and more so if he or she is a personnel of Nigeria's Anti corruption Institutions. Judiciary Institutions The judiciary occupies an important position in every society. It is the last bastion of hope for the citizenry. It is, therefore, the desire of the general public that at all times, justice is not only done but must be seen to have been done so that whenever the judiciary fails to play its stabilizing role in a society, the institution of State is threatened. Ogbonna(2022). Onya & Eleanya (2016) posited that the Nigeria's judiciary institution has been known for failures in fighting corruption and this has led to loss of public trust, hence, they believe that President Buhari's Anti corruption policy will not be a reality but an illusion. Flowing from the preceding of Ogbonna, on the role of judiciary in every society and that of Onya & Eleanya in particular on the failure role of the Nigeria's judiciary institutions in fighting corruption; this paper is of the position that the Nigeria's judiciary institutions has failed in its role to fight corruption in Nigeria's Anticorruption Institutions.because it lacked morality or moral justice and moral correctness. Hence, its bedeviled with ills from corruption to abuse of power, delay in conclusion of corruption trials owing largely to unnecessary adjournments and unmeritorious appeals, perversions of justice, wrongful convictions and acquittal of guilty parties (Ogidi, Egobueze, & Nwaoburu, 2024). This situations has engendered lack of trust in Nigeria's judiciary institutions, thus, the citizenry, that lack morality or moral correctness now will instead resort to more corruption that will compound Nigeria's Anticorruption Institutions failure to fight corruption. However, for better understanding of the role of Nigeria's judiciary institutions in the fight against corruption, this paper will look at conceptual explications of the Nigeria's judiciary institutions, aside Onya & Eleanya'(2016) position earlier posited and take a position in its recommendations as regards its failures in fighting corruption. In doing this, we shall give an explanation of what judicial institutions means and its role generally.Judiciary institutions refer to the system of courts and tribunals that interpret and apply the law in a country or jurisdiction. Judiciary institutions play a vital role in upholding the rule of law, protecting individual rights, and promoting justice. They provide a forum for resolving disputes, interpreting the law, and holding government and other entities accountable for their actions.

The question this paper shall be asking, thus, is, "if Nigeria's Judiciary Institutions will keep faith with its constitutional moral roles in fighting corruption, if the heads of the judiciary are meticulously and meritoriously selected by its professional members to head its institutions and if anti- corruption institutions appointments and selections were made by its professional members? In answering the question, we shall be drawing linkages from Aliyu(2022) pronouncements of three Supreme Court Justices as quoted on a corruption case in Nigeria's Supreme Court: YAKUBU V. FRN (2022) LPELR-57749(SC) as in a paper titled: THE IMPACTS OF CORRUPTION ON ADMINISTRATION OF JUSTICE IN NIGERIA; BY DR MUSA ADAMU ALIYU, HONOURABLE ATTORNEY GENERAL/COMMISSIONER FOR JUSTICE, JIGAWA STATE. AT THE 1ST ANTI-CORRUPTION SUMMIT ORGANISED BY KANO STATE ANTI-CORRUPTION INSTITUTE ON 9TH DECEMBER, 2022.

1. The first pronouncement according to the paper was from Hon. Justice M.D. Mohammad and it states "If this contrary (sic) must survive and provide for the yearnings and aspirations of its honest, hardworking and productive citizens, all its wise sincere and responsible minds and hands must ceaselessly fight corruption. We cannot afford to fail. The trial Court's sentence of a manifestly corrupt person, who inspite of the trust he enjoyed in the position he held, shamelessly stole this country dry to say the least, is preposterous. The lower Court's intervention is a remarkably commendable enforcement of decency. It cannot be interfered with."¹ Hon. Justice M.D. Muhammad, Justice of the Supreme Court of Nigeria.

2. To Hon Justice Tijjani Abubakar, he pronounced that "...I think the time has come for us as a Nation to embark on meticulous scrutiny of proceeds of crime in the hands of offenders to ensure that they go home dry with nothing, this will show that there is no incentive in stealing public funds, it is unfortunate that, all efforts to ensure total restitution is hardly achieved as acknowledged by the Legislative Guide to the United Nations Convention against

Transnational Organized Crimes and the Protocols thereto ... As a nation, we must continue in our efforts to show that crime does not pay, we can only achieve so doing if the Court even where there is a contraption in the name of plea bargain takes proactive steps to ensure that criminals are totally and completely stripped of proceeds of crime." Hon. Justice Tijjani Abubakar, Justice of the Supreme Court of Nigeria.

3. The pronouncement of Honourable Justice Adamu Jauro states that "... eradicating corruption or reducing it to the barest minimum, our judicial institutions must take that giant stride to make fearless pronouncements as done by the Court below. It is the duty of the Court in joint task with our law enforcement agencies to make crime less attractive. It is infuriating that a Civil Servant will embezzle such a humongous sum which was meant to be held in public trust. Ex- Police Officers who have done nothing but dutifully serve this country for years are left to die in the abyss of penury just because an unscrupulous individual in connivance with others chose to fraudulently convert monies they were meant to keep in public trust". Hon. Justice Adamu Jauro, Justice of the Supreme Court of Nigeria. From the pronouncements of the three Supreme Court of Nigeria's Honorable Justices on the referral corruption cases linked in this study above, this paper is of the position that the functions of the appointments and selections of officials who shall be heads of judiciary and anti-corruption institutions should only be done by their professionals meticulously and meritoriously without interference and influence of the Head of Government in order for Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions not to be failures in fighting corruption. Nigeria's Anti-corruption Institutions This section of the paper shall explain the concept of anti-corruption firstly before further discourse on Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions that is a failure in fighting corruption as at the time of this study. This is so because, it will enable us to have better understanding of the subject matter. According to Transparency International, "anti-corruption is the activities intended to prevent or reduce corruption. While corruption refers to the abuse of entrusted power for private gain" (<https://www.transparency.org>) accessed 20/12/'24. Similarly, in order to understand this subject matter better and to add more value to it, this paper shall itemize the goals of anti-corruption in the following order:

- i. Prevention of corrupt practices from occurring in the first place;
- ii. Identifying and exposing corrupt activities;
- iii. Holding individuals and organizations accountable for corrupt actions in accordance with the prescribed law;
- iv. Recovery of stolen assets and funds.

Deriving from the above, this study, is of the position that anti- corruption refers to the actions, policies, and practices aimed at preventing, detecting, and punishing actors involved in corruption. While corruption itself refers to the abuse of power or position for personal gain, that often involves bribery, embezzlement, nepotism, or other forms of illicit act. In Nigeria, the major anti-corruption institutions with mandates include the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC), The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB), the Bureau of Public Procurement (BPP), the Nigerian Extractive Industries, (NEI). The Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Act 2000 (Act 2000) brought a fresh and decisive perspective to the fight against corruption in the form of a holistic approach encompassing enforcement, prevention and educational measures. It captures in a single document, a host of corrupt offences in their old and sophisticated guises. It sets up the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission with wide-ranging powers.

The Act brings under its purview all Nigerians, in the private and public sectors and even those public officers with constitutional immunity, thus, it will be the referral institution to this study. The Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission was inaugurated on September 29th, 2000 by the Nigerian President, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo. The Commission is at the hub of Nigeria's fight against

corruption. In the order set out at section 6 of the Act 2000, the first duty of the Commission is to receive complaints, investigate and prosecute offenders. Its other duties includes reviewing and modifying the systems and procedures of public bodies as well as education of the public and fostering their support in combating corruption. As provided in Section 3(3) of the Act 2000, the Commission consists of a Chairman and twelve (12) Members, two of whom represent each of the six geo-political zones of the country. The membership is drawn from the following categories of Nigerians as spelt out by the Act:

- i. A retired Police Officer not below the rank of Commissioner of Police;
- ii. A legal practitioner with at least 10 years post-call experience;
- iii. A retired Judge of a superior court of record;
- iv. A retired Public Servant not below the rank of a Director;
- v. A woman;
- vi. A youth not being less than 21 or more than 30 years of age at the time of his or her appointment; and
- vii. A chartered accountant. The Act provides that the Chairman and Members of the Commission, who shall be persons of proven integrity, shall be appointed by the President upon confirmation by the Senate and

shall not begin to discharge their duties until they have declared their assets and liabilities as prescribed in the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The tenure of office for the Chairman is five (5) years while that of the Members is four (4) years in the first instance. The Act also provides for the position of a Secretary to the Commission who is to be appointed by the President. The Commission is granted the powers to appoint, deploy, discipline and determine the conditions of service of its staff. Section 3 (14) of the Act enshrines the independence of the Commission by providing that “the Commission shall in the discharge of its functions under this Act, not be subject to the direction or control of any other person or authority” (ICPC Act 2000).

III. CAUSES OF ITS FAILURE

The Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) that was inaugurated on September 29th, 2000 by the Nigerian President then, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo, became a failure because of the following factors among others already discussed: administrative problems; existing foundational anti-corruption documents or laws; corruption in the judiciary; corruption in the commission and executive impunity. The study shall focus on the failure of the first prosecuted case of the Commission because of its embodiment of the five factors and all other factors that represents the failure of Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions to fight corruption. The ICPC's first prosecution took place in 2001, when in a highly publicised trial, four individuals were docked for allegedly offering of 3.5 million naira in gratification to a member of the Justice Obiora Nwazota Commission of Inquiry Panel, established by the Federal Government on the Nigerian Airways Limited (NAL). The accused persons included, one Milton Ohwovoriole, holder of the highest legal professional honour, SAN, Chief Adebisi Olafisoye, a multi-millionaire broker and owner of Fidelity Bond Limited, a reputable financial institution and a manager in his company, Adeyemi Omowunmi. The trio were said to have conspired to offer the sum through Omowunmi, to one Mika Anache, a member of the Justice Obiora Nwazota Commission of Inquiry Panel.

The goal, according to the receiver, Anache, who admitted Omowunmi brought the money which he claimed was from his boss, Olafisoye, for him and other members of the Justice Nwazota Commission of Inquiry Panel, was to wrest a favourable report from the panel, which for over nine months unravelled the decades of wroth in the Nigerian Airways Limited (NAL). Anache, a member of the ruling Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) and the Presidential Committee that reviewed the 1999 constitution, said he kept the money in his bank account for two months, because the commission was on recess, but failed to disclose this until when the commission resumed, only to admit receiving the money when another member of the commission raised the issue that he learnt a commission member had taken 3.5 million naira in gratification. This constitutes an offence under the Act (ICPC Act 2000). All the accused persons, were charged under the Act, though they denied any knowledge of the gratification. Given the social backgrounds of the accused persons, in this first antigraft case, it was thought that the trial was a timely warning to the public, that the Act and commission will not be hostage to the unwritten, but abiding solidarity between the bar and the bench and that party loyalty might not shield anyone from facing prosecution under the present dispensation (Enweremadu, 2012). Unfortunately however, this promising

trial, like others which followed, has remained stalled in the court process till date. More ironical, the principal suspect in the trial, Omowunmi who allegedly ferried the money in question to Alhaji Anache, disappeared from police custody, in what the police describe as 'mysterious circumstances'.

Thereby further compounding the case for the ICPC (Ibid). From the failure of the above analysis of the first prosecuted case by the first and for most anti-corruption institution, Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) that possesses all the requisites in its Act of 2000 to fight corruption in order to put an end to Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions failures in fighting corruption. This paper, thus, is of the position that its obvious that other cases in Nigeria's anti corruption institutions may follow same failure method if the application of morality is not applied to fight corruption in Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions.

IV. Conclusion

The paper identified the major gap that caused the failures of Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions to fight corruption. Thus, it concludes after diligent observation and considerations of the analysis of the factors elucidated in it and in particular the Act 2000 that established Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) that the major gap that needed to be filled is the application of morality or moral correctness and moral justice in Nigeria's anti- corruption institutions, so as to forestall their failures.

V. Recommendations

After due consideration of the analytical discourse in this study, the following recommendations are made: Prebendal system or Prebendalism The paper recommends that the act of prebendal system or prebendalism in selections and appointments of officials in Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions and judiciary systems is one of the factors that contributed to the failure of Nigeria's anti corruption institutions failure to fight corruption. Thus, the principles of morality should be applied in Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions and the judiciary system in order to forestall failures in Nigeria's anti corruption institutions fight against corruption.

Family values: The family is a fundamental institution that plays an integral role in shaping the moral values, beliefs, and character of its members. This is achieved through norms, emotional support, socialization and role modeling. Families transmit moral values and establish norms to guide members to make responsible choices. As the first point of contact for children. families lay the foundation for moral development, influencing individuals to become responsible and morally upright members of society. The family values are recommended so as to forestall Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions failures in fighting corruption.

Judiciary Institutions: The Judiciary institutions in Nigeria has been accused of failures in fighting corruption and this is in lines with the findings of this paper. Hence, this paper recommends that the functions of appointing and selection of the judiciary officials should be done in line with moral correctness and justice by its professionals meticulously and meritoriously without government interference in order to ascertain such member's morality to fight corruption in Nigeria's anti- corruption institutions.

Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions: The paper recommends that the functions of selections and appointments of the anti-corruption institutions officials should be carried out by professionals of the institutions, in line with morality. This should be the method in order to ascertain their moral suitability to fight corruption in Nigeria's Anticorruption institutions.

This paper is of the position that if the above recommendations are followed, the gap created in Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions failures to fight corruption shall be forestalled.

VI. Contribution to knowledge

From all empiricisms of the lucid conceptual explication analysis of the study, one can scientifically assert that the study has indeed contributed the followings to knowledge:

1. The morality principles and relevancies to fight corruption in Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions; has been identified as the gap created by other studies that this study has now filled.

2. The filling of this gap is the hallmark of this study's contribution to Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions fight against corruption. This is so because the application of morality principles and relevancies in filling the gap will sure be a colossal contributory factor in fighting corruption in Nigeria's anti-corruption institutions.

3. Its contribution to knowledge shall be used to enhance futuristic studies in the academia arena in solving related research problems.
4. As in terms of Nigeria political economy development, this study has opined a new window that will enhance stability, efficiency, sanity, productivity and growth through the application of morality principles and relevances. Thus, investors will be encouraged to invest in Nigeria's economy without fear of loosing their investments.
5. Furthermore, the application of morality principles and relevances in all the levels of Nigeria's government and politics institutions and in particular, her anticorruption institutions will sure change her negative inter and intra corruption narratives among her citizens and the international communities. Thus making her to be respected among her citizens and the international communities.
6. The Multinational National Companies (MNC) and the private cooperations won't be left out as regards what this study will contribute to their economic development. The implementation of morality principles and relevancies on their recruitments will sure lead to significant maximization of their goals as the workers will be in a good state of moral correctness to perform optimally in the cause of their duties. Hence, corruption will be mitigated and replaced with morality.
7. In consideration of the above contributions that this study will contribute to knowledge, it's apt to equally note in addition that insecurity that has ravaged the Nigeria's economy and social political life due greatly to corruption will tremendously be minimized because of this study.

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